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A Case Study of the Waste Flow Analysis and Resource Optimization strategies in Selected Textile and Apparel Industries in Export Processing Zone - Biyagama, Sri Lanka

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The apparel export sector is a significant contributor to the Sri Lankan economy that accounts for a contribution of 32% of the gross domestic production (GDP) in 2018 and 48% of total exports according to 2022 records. However, Sri Lanka's textile and apparel sector generates waste in large quantities. This study aimed at identifying the main waste streams and their average waste generation in Biyagama Export Processing Zone (BEPZ), Sri Lanka. The study also focused on waste characteristics and waste disposal methods implemented in BEPZ. Three different sub-sectors of the textile and apparel industry were selected for the study, which comprised five fabric mills, five garment washing and dyeing plants, and ten apparel manufacturing plants. Questionnaires, interviews, and field observations were used for the data gathering process. Results revealed that the average total waste generation was 2376.42 t/year in a fabric mill, 745.88 t/year in a garment washing and dyeing plant, and 429.38 t/year in an apparel manufacturing plant. The average hazardous waste generation percentages in a fabric mill and a garment washing and dyeing plant were 48% and 78%, respectively. Effluent treatment plant (ETP) sludge was identified as the most common form of waste type in fabric mills and garment washing and dyeing plants. However, fabric and yarn waste were the most common waste type in apparel manufacturing plants. Ninety percent of ETP sludge was incinerated, with the remaining 10% being disposed of in landfills. Fabric and yarn waste are reused, exported for recycling and landfilling in percentages of 30%, 20%, and 50%, respectively. The study identified waste types that have monetary value, in each sub-sector. It was revealed that there are significant opportunities for waste utilization within circular economy prospects.

Keywords: Circular Economy, Waste Disposal, Waste Characteristics